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RECOMMENDATIONS FOR LEVERAGING BLUE SPACE FOR HEALTH

A BLUEPRINT FOR CHANGE

University for the Common Good

Blue & Green Wellbeing
Research Group

Net Zero - Scottish Water Sector

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FOREWORD

People are drawn to water, whether sea, river, loch, canal, waterfall or fountain, we love its dynamic, mercurial, life-affirming and reflective qualities. It is life-giving, life-saving, and can be life-threatening, if not treated with respect. We are in awe of its power – at times serene and tranquil and at times angry and foreboding. Clean water is a prerequisite for a healthy life well-lived. And yet we abuse it and often deny access to it for the disadvantaged and less privileged in our society, seeing it instead as a resource to be commodified. Who has not come across the locked gate bearing the sign “Private Property – Keep out!”, thankfully less prominent in Scotland than in other parts of the UK.

The quantum of water on earth is fixed, there is plenty for all if we would only cease polluting it with contaminants and plastic and instead manage it well, learn to live with it, share it and respect it.

These recommendations are founded on the fundamental proposition that blue spaces are of vital importance for healthy cities. In a research programme over several years, the team led by Glasgow Caledonian University has shown that living near blue spaces is good for physical and mental well-being and they have documented these benefits in respect of health equity using the canals of North Glasgow as their laboratory. This work has shown that regeneration may have been the principal driver, but better health has been one of the most significant outcomes.

The qualities of water purity, accessibility for all and good health are why the work documented in this report is important for everyone who works with water as part of their planning, design and management of neighbourhoods and cities. There is no better way to encapsulate this than the team’s clarion call of “look after water, it will look after us”.

PROF BRIAN EVANS PHD

Professor of Urbanism & Landscape

**THE GLASGOW
SCHOOL OF ARE**

CityUrbanist\Glasgow

SCOTLAND PIONEERS URBAN BLUE SPACES FOR HEALTH

BACKGROUND

Urban blue spaces are a vital part of healthy cities. Urban blue spaces can take many forms, from canals to rivers, ponds, lakes and coastlines in cities. Extensive longitudinal research at Glasgow Caledonian University has found mounting evidence for the health benefits of urban blue spaces. Living near urban blue spaces is associated with a lower risk of mortality, higher self-rated health, higher self-reported mental health and wellbeing and a decrease in BMI. These benefits are achieved through four main mechanisms; physical activity, socialisation, stress reduction, and improved environmental conditions.

In addition to the health benefits of urban blue spaces, cities which protect and value their water environments can generate synergistic returns on investment, such as improved water quality, quality of place, reduced healthcare costs and climate change mitigation.

These co-benefits recognise the value that urban blue spaces have on the lives of urban residents in Scotland; fostering them is fundamental to actualising Scotland as a Hydro Nation. This Blueprint responds to the national and international need for concise, evidence-based guidance of practical and feasible policy actions to ensure urban blue spaces work for health and health inequality. It also responds to a need for health-in-all policies and promotes a whole systems approach to achieve a paradigm shift in how blue spaces are understood.

The Blueprint was co-created by researchers, key stakeholders across multiple sectors including health, the government, water management, transport, urban design, civil society, academia and the private sector.

CURRENT SITUATION

In Scotland, physical inactivity is one of the leading causes of premature death. Additionally, obesity levels remain high across Scotland, with two in three adults classified as overweight or obese. Mental health statistics are equally alarming and not equally distributed; there were twice as many GP consultations for anxiety in areas of deprivation than in more affluent areas in Scotland (Audit Scotland, 2012). Emerging evidence suggests that there has been an increase in poor mental health in Scotland throughout the pandemic, particularly among those with pre-existing mental illness, healthcare workers, people who have had exposure to COVID-19 and females (PHS, 2020).

Climate change has been linked to a rise in floods, wildfires, and superstorms, all of which can profoundly harm human health. Climate change is being felt in Scotland and will continue to affect the existence of individual species and Scotland's unique landscapes, as well as our economy, culture and lifestyles. Many of the changes needed to address planetary health can potentially synergistically deliver improved population health outcomes.

Urban blue spaces have the potential to be part of the solution to these complex planetary health and public health challenges.

SYNERGISTIC OPPORTUNITIES AND BENEFITS

No one policy will make urban blue spaces work for health. Instead, a whole system approach is required, incorporating a strategic combination of “upstream” policy actions to make blue spaces work for health at a cultural, economic and environmental level and “downstream” actions focused on individual behaviour change.

We are aware from experience that health is frequently seen as a secondary benefit, not initially considered when working on projects around blue spaces. We advocate for health in all policies approach from the outset.

This Blueprint sets out four strategic objectives, achievable through 12 policy actions. It recognises that the revitalisation of blue spaces requires context-specific interventions, but delivering on as many of the 12 actions as possible will allow the best return on investment. The objectives are presented independently, but the benefits achieved from the actions may cross all four mechanisms.

AIM

TO SUPPORT DECISION-MAKERS TO PROTECT, REVITALISE AND USE URBAN BLUE SPACES IN A WAY THAT PROVIDES SYNERGISTIC BENEFITS TO PEOPLE AND THE PLANET.

BENEFITS OF URBAN BLUE SPACE

Stress reduction

Fresh water storage

Improved self-reported mental health and wellbeing

Improved air quality

Reduced noise pollution

Increased self-reported general health

Reduced flood risk

Increased physical activity

Protection from coastal erosion

Lower BMI

Reduced urban heat island

Increased socialisation

Carbon storage

Support livelihoods

Sense of community

Habitat for wildlife

IMPACT OF BLUE SPACE ON HEALTH AND HEALTH EQUITY

Researchers at GCU have extensively researched the health impacts of the regeneration of canals in North Glasgow. This is the largest natural experiment around a blue space, where the regeneration of the canal was the only recognisable intervention. North Glasgow has some of the most economically deprived communities in Scotland and is affected by compounded poor health outcomes.

Since the 2000s, the canals in North Glasgow have undergone significant changes, including the 'Smart Canal' - tackling flooding in North Glasgow; hundreds of new homes; a watersports complex; a local nature reserve; a skatepark; a cultural and creative hub; and the Stockingfield Bridge which connects three communities and the city centre.

Health was never a primary indicator of success for any of the above projects. However, findings from GCU's work indicate that the canal's regeneration has significantly impacted the local community's health.

Canal through North Glasgow highlighted on a Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD) map

Research in partnership with:

**THE
DATA LAB**

**Scottish
Canals**

GLASGOW Safe Haven
SECURE NHS DATA RESEARCH

IMPACT OF BLUE SPACE ON HEALTH AND HEALTH EQUITY

A systematic review and meta-analysis of global literature on blue space and health found that living within 500m of a blue space led to:

Smith et al. 2021

A further systematic review found that blue space affects health through four key mechanisms:

Georgiou et al. 2021

IMPACT OF BLUE SPACE ON HEALTH AND HEALTH EQUITY

A group of studies conducted with 17 years of NHS health data found that:

The death rate in neighbouring communities has lowered since the canal was regenerated

Tieges et al. 2020

Living within 700m of a blue space in a deprived community leads to

700m

3% Annual reduction in mortality rate

10% Lower risk of obesity

12% Lower risk of diabetes

15% Lower risk of cardiovascular disease, stroke or hypertension.

Tieges et al. 2021

Living near blue space is a protective factor against the mental health risks caused by socio-economic deprivation by up to 6%.

Georgiou et al. 2022

URBAN BLUE SPACES AS THERAPEUTIC LANDSCAPES

Research conducted with >200 people along the canals in North Glasgow found the canals to be therapeutic landscapes:

“definitely keeps you fit, it gets you out and about”

“

“I suffer from depression and anxiety, and the canal is a good way of getting out the house. It’s a nice way of meeting people, they’re all friendly and chatty and it’s nice –it’s like being in the countryside”

”

“you’ve got the calm you can switch off and just take in the nature”

“

“natural artery...a bit like a lung”

Smith et al. 2022

EXPECTED IMPACTS

MECHANISMS

Georgiou et al. 2022

OBJECTIVES

1 Urban blue spaces that support physical activity

2 Urban blue spaces that support social interaction

3 Urban blue spaces that support mental health and wellbeing

4 Urban blue space that support the environment

PARTNERSHIPS FOR ACTION

A HOST OF ORGANISATIONS WERE INVITED TO CONTRIBUTE TO THIS BLUEPRINT INCLUDING:

Given that the objectives and proposed action are beyond the scope of any single agency, implementation necessitates partnership. By working together to achieve the vision of the action plan and improve health for all, adopters of the actions can synergistically meet their own goals and make blue spaces work for health.

These organisations represent a diverse range of sectors, including health, government, third sector, water management, transport, urban design, civil society, academia and the private sector.

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT
MUST BE INTEGRAL TO THE
MANAGEMENT AND
REVITALISATION OF BLUE
SPACES.

OBJECTIVE 1

SUPPORT PHYSICAL ACTIVITY

Three policy actions are proposed to promote and foster physical activity for all ages and abilities through fit-for-purpose infrastructure, personal opportunities and capacity building.

1.1

BUILD SUSTAINABLE, WELL MAINTAINED, FIT FOR PURPOSE INCLUSIVE INFRASTRUCTURE

1.2

CREATE OPPORTUNITIES FOR PEOPLE TO BE ACTIVE IN, ON AND NEAR WATER

1.3

BUILD CAPACITY IN LOCAL POPULATION TO USE BLUE SPACES FREELY, SAFELY AND RESPONSIBLY

OBJECTIVE 2

SUPPORT SOCIAL INTERACTION

Three policy actions are proposed to position urban blue spaces as social spaces by providing appropriate infrastructure, opportunity and community-building initiatives.

2.1

BUILD INFRASTRUCTURE THAT INVITES SOCIAL INTERACTION, INCLUDING SPACES TO SIT AND SPACES WITH SHELTER FROM RAIN.

2.2

CREATE OPPORTUNITIES FOR PEOPLE TO SOCIALISE AROUND WATER

2.3

FOSTER A SENSE OF COMMUNITY AROUND BLUE SPACES

OBJECTIVE 3

SUPPORT MENTAL HEALTH AND WELLBEING

Three policy actions are proposed to make blue spaces work for mental health and wellbeing through infrastructure supporting positive mental health, spaces for structured therapy, and spaces to experience the informal therapeutic benefits.

3.1

BUILD INFRASTRUCTURE THAT SUPPORTS POSITIVE MENTAL HEALTH

3.2

INCLUDE SPACE FOR STRUCTURED THERAPY

3.3

PROTECT AND PRESERVE BLUE SPACES TO ENABLE THEM AS THERAPEUTIC LANDSCAPES

OBJECTIVE 4

SUPPORT THE ENVIRONMENT

Three policy actions are proposed around using the environment to improve health directly and indirectly by working synergistically on climate change mitigation, ecosystem services, disease prevention and environmental citizenship.

4.1

ENSURE ANY INTERVENTIONS FOR HUMAN HEALTH SYNERGISTICALLY WORK FOR PLANETARY HEALTH

4.2

EMPLOY ECOSYSTEM SERVICES THAT PREVENT SPREAD OF DISEASE

4.3

PROVIDE OPPORTUNITIES FOR ENVIRONMENTAL CONSERVATION AND HYDROCITIZENSHIP

ACTION PRIORITY MATRIX

Actions can be prioritised using an Action Priority Matrix. The below examples were votes on by workshop attendees.

Actions that are not viable or thankless tasks were dismissed.

The categorising of the actions is specific to local-contexts.

(Use this as a guide to explore specifics within your context)

WHERE DO THESE ACTIONS FIT WITH EXISTING POLICY?

These recommendations complement existing policies and initiatives, both nationally and internationally.

In Scotland, the recommendations align with green infrastructure design, placemaking and economic regeneration initiatives. The recommendations also contribute to parts of Scotland's National Performance Framework by helping people be healthy and active by protecting and enhancing our environment. Similarly, the recommendations can be used in conjunction with the Place Standard Tool, helping to evaluate the quality of public spaces and to guide decision-making around the design and development of new or existing spaces. Similar actions are being proposed in England within the Environmental Improvement Plan.

More widely, the recommendations can be understood in the context of the Sustainable Development Goals.

RESOURCING

The quality of blue space and the engagement of communities are key to delivering the benefits discussed in this document. Urban blue space actions require funding and other resources (time and expertise, for example) to generate and maintain these outcomes. This may be a challenge during a time of pressure on public funds and private businesses. Many, if not all, of the organisations involved in urban regeneration and community outcomes are facing significant resourcing problems, which could result in limited interest in blue space action.

However, the co-benefits that arise from improving and maintaining blue spaces, and supporting people to use them, offer a more constructive and mutually beneficial way forward. There are many synergies between the social, community, environmental and economic outcomes that are being sought across our towns and cities. If we analyse opportunities more holistically and work in a more coordinated way, then it is possible to deliver multifunctional/multi-benefit action much more efficiently than addressing each set of priorities separately. This doesn't mean that everything has to be delivered collectively; it is primarily about agreeing on a shared vision for a place and understanding where actions can be aligned to deliver aligned outcomes.

North Glasgow is an interesting case in point. The regeneration of the canal corridor through a part of the city which has been historically underfunded has demonstrably delivered health benefits and reduced health inequalities along with significant place improvements.

The key players in this transformation included Scottish Canals, Glasgow City Council, local housing associations, NatureScot and the local community. The outcomes that were being sought included placemaking, economic regeneration and sustainable surface water management but a core focus on the community aspiration to have more attractive and better connected community spaces allowed all of the agendas to be brought together and each funder to play its part in a wider suite of activity.

MONITORING AND EVALUATING ACTIONS

Planning actions around urban blue spaces requires us to carefully think about how we will monitor and evaluate their success. Evaluation processes should be well-planned and we must understand the baseline data before any actions commence. This way we can look at the before and after data to identify what changes occurred as a result of the actions.

Examples of baseline data include:

- Demographics
- Health Statistics
- Perceptions of the space
- Environmental quality surveys

Such data can be collected through desk research or through surveys and/or interviews with local populations.

WHILE PLANNING NEW ACTIONS, IT IS CRUCIAL TO DECIDE ON WHAT DATA YOU WILL COLLECT TO MONITOR AND EVALUATE IMPACT.

COLLECTING BASELINE DATA MEANS WE CAN ACCURATELY MEASURE THE IMPACT OF OUR ACTIONS.

HOW DID WE DEVELOP THIS BLUEPRINT?

PHASE	DESCRIPTION
PHASE 01	Extensive academic research undertaken at Glasgow Caledonian University on the health benefits of urban blue spaces
PHASE 02	Partnered with Hydro Nation to learn from their expertise in policy and reduce siloed working
PHASE 03	System-based participatory research and co-creation process with diverse range of stakeholders

SUMMARY

This document has provided 12 recommendations for leveraging blue spaces to promote health and wellbeing. Blue spaces have been shown to have a positive impact on mental and physical health. The recommendations highlight the importance of engaging with local communities to ensure that blue spaces are accessible and inclusive. This includes working with community groups to identify their needs and preferences, as well as promoting local ownership and stewardship of these spaces.

Additionally, the document emphasises the need for collective action and collaboration among stakeholders to maximise the benefits of blue spaces. This includes working with different partners across the system to develop coordinated actions. The recommendations also stress the importance of monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of interventions, and sharing best practices and lessons learned.

Ultimately, by engaging with local communities and working collectively, the recommendations aim to promote sustainable and equitable use of blue spaces to improve public health while simultaneously preserving the planet.

APPENDICES

Blue & Green Wellbeing Research Group

Portfolio

Meet the Team

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Blue & Green Wellbeing Research Group

Portfolio

List of Publications

- **Environmentally informed pharmaceutical prescribing in Scotland: Current policy landscape and proposed policy options to enable the implementation of eco-directed pharmaceutical prescribing in the Scottish healthcare system** (Policy Brief & Policy Note)

Alejandre, J.C., Frascaroli, G., Escudero, A., Pahl, O., Price, L., Pflieger, S., & Helwig, K., *Scotland's Centre of Expertise for Waters (CREW)*, (2022)

- **Urban Blue Spaces as Therapeutic Landscapes: "A Slice of Nature in the City"**

Smith, N., Foley, R., Georgiou, M., Tiegies, Z., & Chastin, S., *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, Vol. 19, Page 15018, 19(22), 15018., (2022)

- **Does living near blue space modify the effect of socioeconomic deprivation on mental health in urban areas: a population-based retrospective study** (Conference Abstract)

Georgiou, M., Tiegies, Z., Morison, G., Smith, N., & Chastin, S., *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 6, S6., (2022)

- **Investigating the contextual factors and mechanisms associated with implementing Blue Prescription Programmes in health and social care settings: a systematic review using realist synthesis** (Conference Abstract)

Alejandre, J. C., Chastin, S., Irvine, K. N., Georgiou, M., Khanna, P., Tiegies, Z., Smith, N., Chong, Y. Y., Onagan, F. C., Price, L., Pflieger, S., Helliwell, R., Singleton, J., Estandarte, A., Smith, E. S., Curran, S., & Helwig, K., *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 6, S9., (2022)

- **A population-based retrospective study of the modifying effect of urban blue space on the impact of socioeconomic deprivation on mental health, 2009–2018**

Georgiou, M., Tiegies, Z., Morison, G., Smith, N., & Chastin, S., *Nature Scientific Reports* 12:1, 12(1), 1–11. (2022)

- **Investigating the association between regeneration of urban blue spaces and risk of incident chronic health conditions stratified by neighbourhood deprivation: A population-based retrospective study, 2000–2018**

Tiegies, Z., Georgiou, M., Smith, N., Morison, G., & Chastin, S., *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health*, 240, 113923. (2022)

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List of Publications

- **Factors influencing usage of urban blue spaces: A systems-based approach to identify leverage points**
Smith, N., Georgiou, M., King, A. C., Tiegies, Z., & Chastin, S., *Health & Place*, 73, 102735. (2022)
- **Urban blue spaces and human health: A systematic review and meta-analysis of quantitative studies**
Smith, N., Georgiou, M., King, A. C., Tiegies, Z., Webb, S., & Chastin, S., *Cities*, 119, 103413. (2021)
- **Mechanisms of Impact of Blue Spaces on Human Health: A Systematic Literature Review and Meta-Analysis**
Georgiou, M., Morison, G., Smith, N., Tiegies, Z., & Chastin, S., *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, (2021)
- **Understanding the contexts and mechanisms of bluespace prescription programmes implemented in health and social care settings: a realist review**
Alejandre, J. C., Chastin, S., Irvine, K. N., Georgiou, M., Khanna, P., Tiegies, Z., Smith, N., Chong, Y.-Y., Onagan, F. C., Price, L., Pflieger, S., Helliwell, R., Singleton, J., Curran, S., & Helwig, K., *MedRxiv*, 2021.10.15.21264908, (2021)
- **"Kids Get in Shape with Nature": A Systematic Review Exploring the Impact of Green Spaces on Childhood Obesity**
Alejandre, J.C. and Lynch, M., *Journal of Nutritional Science and Vitaminology*, 66 (Supplement), S129-S133, (2022)
- **The Impact of Regeneration and Climate Adaptations of Urban Green-Blue Assets on All-Cause Mortality: A 17-Year Longitudinal Study**
Tiegies, Z., McGregor, D., Georgiou, M., Smith, N., Saunders, J., Millar, R., Morison, G., & Chastin, S., *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(12), 1–12., (2020)
- **Child-centered and nutrition-sensitive green spaces: policy recommendations for childhood obesity prevention in the Philippines**
Alejandre, J.C., Algonos, P.J., Soluta, N., Henry, R., & Lynch, M., *Harvard Public Health Review Journal*, (2022) (in press)

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Conferences

- **One Health Breakthrough Partnership: Project Group Meeting**, December 2019 (Online) (1 Talk)
- **NVivo Virtual Conference: Qualitative Research in a Changing World**, September 2020 (Online) (1 Poster)
- **SFG Hydration Spring Meeting (World Water Day)**, April 2021 (Online) (1 Poster)
- **International Water Association UK Young Water Professional Conference: Tapping into the Future**, April 2021 (London, England) (1 Talk)
- **The 2021 System Dynamics Conference**, July 2021 (Online) (1 Poster)
- **SFG Hydration Welcome Event**, November 2021 (Edinburgh, Scotland) (1 Poster, 1 Talk)
- **CleanMed Europe Conference – Designing Tomorrow’s Healthcare**, November 2021 (Online) (1 Talk)
- **One Health Breakthrough Partnership: Project Oversight Group Meeting**, September 2021 (Online) (1 Talk)
- **International Medical Geography Symposium**, June 2022 (Edinburgh, Scotland) (1 Poster, 1 Talk)
- **European Conference of Mental Health**, September 2022 (Lisbon, Portugal) (1 Talk)
- **GCU School Health and Life Sciences Post Graduate Research Student Conference**, September 2022, (Glasgow, Scotland) (1 Talk)
- **Planetary Health Annual Meeting**, October 2022 (Boston, US) (3 Posters, 1 Talk)
- **Urban Transitions 2022**, November 2022 (Sitges, Spain) (2 Posters, 1 Talk)
- **World One Health Congress**, October 2020 (Online) (1 Poster)
- **Ecosystem Services Partnership Europe Conference**, June 2021 (Tallin, Estonia) (1 Talk)
- **Scotland’s World Water Day Meeting**, March 2021, (Online) (1 Poster)
- **Scotland’s World Water Day Meeting**, March 2020, (Online) (1 Poster)
- **NHS Tayside Grand Rounds**, October 2021, (Dundee, Scotland) (1 Talk)
- **British Council Workshop on Nature-Based Public Health Interventions**, July 2022, (Leipzig, Germany) (1 Talk)

Blue & Green Wellbeing Research Group

Portfolio

Press Impact

- The World Economic Forum (WEF) celebrates World Water Day 2021 showcasing our work on blue spaces!
- Our work on the mechanisms of the impact of blue spaces featured by The Independent!
- Julius Cesar Alejandro describes how social prescribing of green/blue spaces could be an effective strategy to battle the mental health crisis in the Philippines, on CNN Philippines!
- Professor Sebastien Chastin explains how living near blue spaces can save lives on Radio New Zealand!
- Julius Cesar Alejandro joins the The Washington Post to discuss the stress relieving effects of blue spaces and how they can be effectively prescribed!
- Professor Sebastien Chastin joins the Nature & Wellbeing Symposium 2021 by the Ministry for the Environment of the government of New Zealand and discusses the influence of blue spaces on human health!
- Michail Georgiou shares the team's research in an interview by Sarah Sloat for Inverse online magazine!
- Dr. Zoë Tiegas joins the GCU Common Good Podcast to discuss how living near canals can cut the risk of chronic illnesses!

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Press Impact

- Niamh Smith is interviewed by Ian Hamilton and shares her thoughts about the 20-min neighbourhoods, on BBC Scotland!
- Michail Georgiou joins the GCU Common Good Podcast to discuss how living near blue spaces can reduce the risk of mental health conditions and narrow inequalities!
- Julius Cesar Alejandro explains how the use of blue spaces in social prescribing can "take away the blues" of the COVID-19 pandemic, at the Hydronation International Centre!
- BBC highlights our blue space findings and Niamh Smith explains what they mean!
- Niamh Smith joins Cape Talk Radio to discuss the benefits of blue spaces for our health!
- 'More bins, better lighting' Article in Glasgow Times highlighting research led by Niamh Smith
- Blue Space Benefits' Article in Politico highlighting the work of the research unit

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